

Developing Positive Attitude towards Teaching Profession

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Abstract:

Teaching is the noblest among all professions. Teachers help in shaping and reshaping the society and determine the quality of life in the community and the nation. So the teacher quality is crucial issue for the teacher education. To improve the quality of teacher education, competent and committed teacher educators are given due place for pious task of preparing future teachers. There has been rapid growth of education at all level which has resulted into increasing number of teachers as well as more schools. As a result, quality of education was sacrificed for the sake of quantity in education and the teacher education facilities could not be increased in the proportion to the number of teachers needed for the increase in enrolment at school level. As a result, untrained candidates with low academic qualifications were appointed as teachers. The deteriorating condition of teacher education is due to the lack of commitment and positive attitude towards teaching profession. Need of the hour is to have a five year professional course of teacher education after +2 stage and establishment of a national University of Teacher Education.

Key Words: - Positive Attitude, Teaching Profession

Introduction:

The progress of a country depends upon the quality of its teachers and for this reason, teaching is the noblest among all professions as it is also stated in Education

Commission Report, 1964-66 that the destiny of the nation is being shaped only in the classroom. It implies that the teacher who is organiser and controller of the classroom is mostly responsible for the future of India. A competent teacher can bring the entire world in to the classroom. Dr. S. Radhakrishnan aptly said "Until and unless we have dedicated and committed teachers, who can take teaching as a mission in their lives, we cannot have a good educational system. Teacher should be the best minds of the country". But, a teacher can not perform his or her multifarious tasks and responsibilities until he or she is not updated professionally and personally.

Teacher education is an integral component of the educational system. It is intimately connected to the ethos, culture and character of a nation. It is not only meant for teaching the teacher, how to teach but also to kindle his initiative to keep it alive to minimise evils of the "Hit and Miss" process and to save time, energy and money of the teachers and the taught. It would help the teacher to minimize his/her trouble and to discharge his/her responsibilities with efficiency and effectiveness. Teacher education is no longer a training process but an education strategy for enabling teachers to teach and concern for their well-being.

Teacher quality is therefore crucial and has been globally accepted to be significantly associated with the quality of education in general and students' learning outcomes in particular. The National Policy on Education 1986 stated, "No people can rise above the level of its teachers...." Similar sentiments have been expressed by the Delors report (1996), and UNESCO report on *Teacher and Educational Quality: Monitoring Global Needs for 2015(2006)*. The European Commission Report 'Communication on Teacher Education' (2007) in the very beginning observes 'research shows that teacher quality is significantly and positively correlated with pupil attainment and it is the most important within school aspect explaining students' performance(40, p.3). So for the development of the country, it is very important to have good teachers and good teachers can be produced only if we have good system of teacher education and dedicated and efficient teacher educators. During the last sixty years after independence there has been rapid growth of education at all level. The unprecedented increase in enrolment every year needed ever-increasing number of teachers as well as more schools. As a result, quality of education was sacrificed for the sake of quantity in education. Earlier the teacher education facilities could not be

increased in the proportion to the number of teachers needed for the increase in enrolment at school level. As a result, untrained candidates with low academic qualifications were appointed as teachers. Also due to inadequate financial resources, the large number of schools and colleges that were set up could not be properly equipped with educational infrastructure. During last decade there is mushrooming growth of self finance teacher education institutions without any proper infrastructure and teachers began to prepare ill-trained teachers who were merely given the certificate as trained teachers. All this has caused considerable erosion and deterioration in the quality of existing teachers and in the standards of teacher education.

Under such prevailing circumstances the profession of teaching does not enjoy the status as other profession like medicine, engineering, administration, law etc in the society. The role of teacher is changing so fast that the present pre-service or in-service teacher education is not able to cope with the expectation of the society. A teacher can work wonders provided he feels like doing so. From where can that feeling be generated? The first study on the status of teachers in India was done long back by World Confederation of Organization of the teaching profession in 1967. On the basis of the findings, it was concluded that the present status of Indian teachers was quite low because of inadequate salaries, meagre financial resources, limited avenues for promotion and advancement, lack of professional autonomy and lack of political progress.

The teaching profession selected by most of the students is due to the fact that there was no other alternative. So there is no commitment for the profession. NCTE (1998) has pointed out that teacher education programmes shall focus on competencies and commitment in much greater magnitude. It calls for bringing out a transformation in teacher preparation strategies as well as in behavioural challenges in pupils under their charge. A sound programme for professional education of teachers is essential for the qualitative improvement of education. To improve the quality of teacher education, we should not only see that what type of students are selected but it is of vital importance that competent and committed teacher educators are given due place for this pious task of preparing future teachers. It is the role of teacher educators to

prepare future teachers to be life long learners and educational workers to create a learning society. But, teacher educators can play such type of role effectively only if their own education is better and is imparted in a proper manner.

Still the problem persists, the teachers which are produced in teacher education institutions, when they go to school, they do not teach well. They throw all their teaching skills to dustbin immediately after acquiring the training qualification. It so seems that all our efforts to produce effective teachers are in vain if we do not take note of the attitude of teachers towards teaching profession because attitude is directly associated with some eternal values. There was a saying that those who do not get job anywhere become teacher. But in present time the scenario has been changed and those who are preparing for civil services, engineering, medical, defence exam, if not selected there, qualifies for the teacher education course and join this profession as there is a secured government job for B.Ed candidates. Moreover, the attitude formation process towards teaching of a student is lacking right from beginning. Schooling system of our country leads the student to give importance to engineering, medical, law, administrative services as these jobs are termed as prestigious. There are specialised courses like B.Tech. and M.B.B.S from graduation level itself but there is no course for teacher education at graduation level. The teaching profession is neglected by the society because of the less monetary benefits and there is no rapid promotion in the teaching profession. There is corruption in every sphere of the society but a teacher should be sincere, honest and truthful and inspite of that there is no reward for good deed and one has to suffer a lot if he follows a noble path.

In such attitudinal problems, it is quiet impossible for a teacher to love teaching profession as well as students. There are many strategies which may work well to develop positive attitude for teaching. We must redesign our teacher education programme in form of futuristic outlook. It must make a scrutiny of pre-service and in-service education with objectives of education and holistic development of child, the research and development in reshaping teacher education and finally the convergence of national and autonomous bodies involved in reforming teacher education.

Reforms in teacher education has to be considered ranging from pre-primary teacher education to higher secondary teacher education. In the context of NPE (1986) and NCTE recommendations there should be visualisation of profession Teacher Education programmes aiming at the development of teacher as an instrument of social change. The pre-service course in teacher preparation currently in practice include one year programme, B.Ed./M.Ed. While the one year teacher preparation continues to be traditional, the innovative nature of four year integrated pre-service programme of teacher education presently at RIEs and two-year post-graduate programmes with a larger components of school based activities and sustained internship of at least six months need to be launched which are yet to draw the attention of State Governments and Colleges of Teacher Education. Longer duration of pre-service education can be helpful in developing teachers' beliefs and value system so that they become aware of their various pedagogical responsibilities and carry them out effectively, thereby enabling learners to develop into caring and conscientious human beings. Moreover gradual change over from conventional programmes of teacher education to integrated course will ensure greater professionalism and increased duration of teacher education programmes will accommodate for proper assimilation of emerging professional inputs.

Teacher education institutions should be properly equipped in terms of infrastructural facilities and properly trained and qualified staff so that the commitment and competency for preparing teachers for various levels of school education. It is crucially important that Government recognizes the need to provide the right and proper working conditions for teachers. The teaching profession should have a real sense of ownership of its work. NCTE should ensure strict adherence to norms and standards so that the quality of teacher education is not compromised.

The teaching profession must be funded properly and accorded the status it deserves if it is to attract high quality entrants from every section of society. An up-to-date comparison should be made of teaching with a range of other graduate occupations, taking into account pay, training costs, opportunities and early employment experiences, especially for graduates in mathematics, science and technology.

It is high time that the policy makers and government should pay attention towards preparing the quality teachers who are committed to teaching profession. The duration of integrated programme for teacher education after +2 level should be of five years. There is also need of setting up a separate university for teacher education just like Technical University, Law University etc. so that it fully concentrates on the discipline of education and may work for inculcation of commitment and attitude needed for the profession. There must be entrance test at all India level for subject knowledge and teaching aptitude for the admission to the integrated programme. The teacher preparation programme should cover the aspects of attitudinal change, class-room management, changing focus from teaching to learning., creating student-friendly class-room and school atmosphere, effective use of teaching-learning materials and creating such materials by using locally available materials, essentials of pedagogy, alternatives to class-room teaching/learning and basic computer knowledge (use of the computer, surfing the internet, word-processing, etc.)

CONCLUSION

It may be stated by way of conclusion that development of commitment and positive attitude towards teaching profession is of utmost importance in terms of ensuring quality of education in general and students' learning outcome in particular. Teachers are the greatest assets of any education system as they are the interface of the transmission of knowledge, skills and values and are accepted as the backbone of education system. There is urgent need to modify and modernize the pre-service teacher education programme to suit the requirements of contemporary educational needs of the society and instill greater professionalism and commitment.